

How do I get to have glass splashbacks in my kitchen?

The procedure is very simple if you

require the full measuring and

installation service. All you need to

do is make a very basic measure

(no need to be mm perfect) of the

length and height of the area which

you would like to have the glass

splashbacks (or glass upstands if

you simply want a smaller border

e.g. 100mm high) and count a total

figure for the amount of socket cut

outs (if any) required - don't worry about which piece of glass they're in just a total for the entire job (and singles cost exactly the same as

doubles at Kitchen Calm). Also, the thickness of glass nearly always [sparkle splashback](#) used in splashbacks is 6mm but should you require for design or

structural reasons a thicker glass please include this detail with the measurements and socket count.

You then need to call us on either 0845 0450336 or 01642 648444 or alternatively simply send an email to sales@kitchencalm.co.uk with

these measurements. We can then provide a quotation which if you are happy with we would then book a date to attend site and

professionally measure your splashbacks. The colour doesn't need to be chosen at time of quotation and doesn't affect the price of the

splashback unless you would like a metallic/sparkle effect (which you need to make us aware of at time of quote if that's the case).

Supply only or single, e.g. hob, splashback

If you don't require the full service or simply need a single splashback as in a cooker splashback (or hob splashback) then the procedure is much the same as above.

As all of our splashbacks are made to measure it's quite difficult to supply prices here as each piece is different but we are very keen on price and deliver nationwide.

Simply call or email sales@kitchencalm.co.uk with the basic sizes and we'll speedily quote your glass kitchen splashback requirements including fixing silicone (if needed) and delivery.

The lovely colours your splashback could be!

As you are no doubt already completely aware - coloured glass splashbacks are indeed splashbacks which are coloured- and you'll notice as you glance around modern kitchens in the UK, splashbacks are making more and more of an appearance mainly due, arguably, to the wonderful choice of colour.

The choice is huge as the splashbacks are painted (albeit a very special paint) and as such can accommodate virtually any colour in the spectrum. To keep things less daunting though we've selected some glass splashback colours seen by either clicking the colours option at the top or simply by clicking here. Do bear in mind though that should you not like our standard glass splashback colours you can create your own via dulux/farrow&ball/RAL etc...

We also have a small brochure with our standard colours professionally printed (and spot glossed to give the appearance of being behind glass) and will gladly

send a copy if you'd like to email your details to sales@kitchencalm.co.uk

It really should be toughened glass in a kitchen!!

There are many companies supplying toughened and coloured glass to use as kitchen splashbacks but there are equally as many who state that you don't really need to toughen the glass. Or they'll tell you that it only needs to be a toughened splashback behind a hob. Well they can say what they want as we believe very strongly here at Kitchen Calm that all the glass wherever possible should be toughened to British Safety Standards. Once installed it is a much safer product and the only reason not to toughen would be to save on cost but as we have our own toughening plant and don't need to sub the glass out to toughen you would save very little indeed. In our expert (and some would say seasoned) opinion - it really should be toughened glass in a kitchen!!